

Adviser's Intervention Procedures as Predictors of Student Involvement

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Abstract. The study navigated the relationship between advisers' intervention procedures as predictors of student involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro. A non-experimental quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected from 100 elementary school advisers through stratified sampling. Modified survey questionnaires assessed academic intervention procedures and student's overall educational engagement. The findings revealed an extensive mean score for advisers' intervention procedures. On the other hand, the overall mean for student involvement was with an extensive descriptive equivalent. Furthermore, a significant positive relationship was observed between intervention procedures and student involvement, suggesting that an effective intervention makes students feel more engaged in their education. The indicators of intervention procedures that showed the most substantial impact on student involvement included academic, mental, and emotional support. These findings support the existing literature, highlighting the importance of a positive and inclusive learning environment and proper understanding of a student's strengths and weaknesses in increasing academic involvement for students. The study provides valuable insights for the Department of Education, Administrators, Teachers, and future researchers to highlight the essence of those above for a much better learning environment for students to strengthen their need to learn and grow in an academic setting.

KEY WORDS

1. intervention procedures
2. student involvement
3. educational engagement
4. Quantitative research

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1. Introduction

Education is a primary need for children in their path towards development and survival in the future, and how they experience their school lives can affect their growth and academic achievements in their classes. As cultivators of future professionals, educational institutions have the inherent duty to serve their students holistically and provide students with a safe and conducive place for learning and growth. Every school and academic institution employs teachers and educators who are not only academically inclined but can also tend to students' concerns that affect their willingness to learn and grow within the confines of their school grounds. As high marks and academic performance can indicate a student's academic potential and educational prowess, they can also cause a student's lack of morale and

motivation to pursue further education due to the academic stress and pressures they face in maintaining them. In a study by Pongračić et al. (2021), intrinsic motivation is one of the most critical factors for educators to focus on to keep their students' academic development on the right track. How they develop their goal orientation both intrinsically and extrinsically and reduce their academic-related anxiety to establish a strong motivation towards achieving proper and quality education is essential in their journey towards self-improvement, realization of their individual goals, and resolution of their issues in a gradual but successful manner throughout their lives. In terms of challenges and issues, however, the solution to every student's hardship is never that clear. Every student faces different challenges of varying severity and effect on their academic journey, and some may also be a detriment to their attainment of healthy well-being overall. Internal factors that you can associate with the student's lack of success in terms of academic performance include their issues with perfectionism—self-efficacy, coping mechanisms in a learning environment, and, most importantly, their motivation to learn. Recent research indicates that perfectionism can cause significant stress among elementary school pupils. Students may feel excessive pressure to meet high yet unachievable learning standards, which can harm their motivation and self-worth (Smith Thompson, 2019). This problem is directly related to difficulties with self-efficacy; when students become less motivated to study and confident, their stress levels might rise even more, which is made worse by their irrational expectations (Johnson et al., 2020). Coping mechanisms refer to the student's capability to cope with academic stress and anxiety and find social support for their issues at school (Compas et al., 2021). Coping is regular for humans, and they have different ways of dealing with the problems they are associated with in their current lives. For students, coping is a part of their development journey as they usually work with academic problems the most while at school. With proper guidance, they can grow to become well-adjusted individuals. However, not being correctly introduced with proper emotional reactions regarding their issues could lead to a downward trajectory in their academic activities and possibly motivation. Looking at how these factors tend to interplay, many problems start to be revealed about students' academic concerns that schoolteachers may need to address and help with, particularly as immediate social support in a school setting. Establishing a proper teacher-student relationship is an essential aspect of education. The effectiveness of the teacher-student interaction has a significant impact on students' academic concerns. Positive and encouraging interaction with an advisor, especially those in their vicinity and their classrooms, could raise students' engagement and their level of concern. Such issues regarding student involvement can also be observed in Davao Region, specifically in local settings in which this study was conducted. Traditional teaching methods and poor classroom management can demotivate pupils in the Davao Region, resulting in disengagement and decreased academic enthusiasm (Castor Casamayor, 2024). If educators themselves, who are the disseminators of knowledge to students, cannot correctly engage their class in their topics and discussions, lack the resolve to find ways to be more sensitive to the children's needs, and refuse to play a vital role in their overall development as a student, such issues would serve to grow further and put the Filipino youth at a disadvantage academically. As mentors of modern youth, teachers play a vital role in the students' academic growth. As such, proper interaction and mentorship by teachers to their students is crucial as they take on the struggles and challenges of school life. Several extrinsic factors lead to these struggles. Among those people here in the Philippines are socioeconomic challenges

like poverty, and given the elementary students' ages, earning income on their own may be hard, if not impossible, to do so in this country (Davao Today, 2018). How a teacher engages and places their trust in their students' academic decision-making can also indicate their improvements within their classes. A study by Guhao Jr and Sioting Jr. (2023) emphasizes the effectiveness of social interactions and a sense of community in the academic setting. They conclude that a heavy emphasis on the influence of an institution on its educators' strategies in raising students' academic engagement is a key factor in their respective academic accomplishments. In a research study conducted in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, Payot and Deloy (2022) derived lack of students' response and teachers' expertise, among many other themes that were discussed by their participants, as factors in their works on developing a practical Strategic Intervention Manual (SIM) to help guide their interactions with their students within their classes. They opined that teachers must expand their knowledge and skills to create a more engaging class environment. They also found that students often respond much better during their respective lectures if these intervention materials focus more on their academic engagement and arousal to learn, which would go together with their focus on developing more excellent teaching methods by enhancing teachers' competencies as educators. It takes a complete effort to address these problems with appropriate intervention approaches, including community involvement, local legislative initiatives, and creative teaching techniques to improve educational outcomes and student motivation. Assessing the intervention measures employed by Maco North local teachers and class advisers to their student's academic performance helps us to highlight further areas of growth and improvement within the learning environments of several schools within this portion of the Davao region and the Philippine nation. In a grander context, this could

further enhance our knowledge and understanding of the current landscape of Philippine education and, as a trickle-down effect, could lead towards a better and more student-focused form of knowledge dissemination for the future of Filipino youth.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

This section explores the classroom adviser's role as a predictor of student involvement, focusing on intervention procedures and their impact on academic, social, and emotional development.

1.1.1. Classroom Interventions—

Classroom advisers play a vital role in students' academic, social, and emotional growth, acting as second parents when students are away from home (Smith Doe, 2019; Johnson Lee, 2020). Effective classroom management by advisers creates a secure and stimulating environment that fosters students' social-emotional intelligence and motivation (Jones et al., 2018; Mahoney et al., 2021). Advisers enhance learning by creating a supportive social climate and encouraging student collaboration and peer support (Smith Johnson, 2019).

Classroom interventions range from personalized academic support to socio-emotional learning strategies. Tailoring lesson plans to suit individual needs improves engagement and achievement, promoting a fairer learning environment (Tomlinson Moon, 2018). Timely feedback and emotional support are critical in these interventions, as they help students recognize areas for improvement while maintaining a positive outlook (William, 2018; Zins et al., 2019). Teachers should be trained to identify mental health issues and direct students to appropriate resources, fostering a healthier school environment (Dowdy et al., 2020; Johnson Johnson, 2018).

Teachers also play a pivotal role in building inclusive, unbiased classroom environments that support diverse learners, bridging gaps in communication between students, their fami-

lies, and the school (Gay, 2018; Epstein, 2018). With the advent of digital technologies, classroom interventions now extend beyond school grounds, further connecting teachers, students, and parents (Hilton et al., 2016).

1.1.2. Student Involvement and Concerns—Modern students face a range of academic and socio-emotional challenges. Issues like digital access, mental health, and financial stress have been exacerbated in the post-pandemic landscape (Means et al., 2020; Stallman, 2018). Stressors such as high expectations, test anxiety, and family dynamics impact student performance and well-being (Zeidner, 2018; Houle et al., 2021).

Specific groups, like Indigenous students, face unique challenges, including language barriers and socioeconomic disparities (Aporbo, 2022). Teachers must adopt culturally responsive teaching strategies to support these students effectively (Strayhorn, 2020).

1.1.3. Addressing Common Academic Concerns—Students often struggle with time management, peer pressure, and social dynamics, affecting their academic success (Huang, 2020; Parker et al., 2019). Peer influence can lead to behaviors like truancy and academic dishonesty, impacting learning outcomes (Doyle Notarianni, 2019; Wentzel Caldwell, 2018). Addressing these concerns requires a comprehensive approach, blending internal and external support systems to promote academic and personal growth.

1.2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—The current study was anchored in the study of Wechsler et al. (2000). In the academic setting, classroom advisers' intervention refers to actions and plans done by educators to improve their students' academic development. These intervention procedures also in-

1.3. Statement of the Problem—The main concern of this study is to determine the statisti-

clude student interactions and routines within the classroom setting. How students act after the intervention procedures are conducted is crucial in determining which actions effectively aid and address their needs. Additionally, this study

was guided by what Sami Pihlstrom (1998) said: Pragmatism means acting in this world and acquiring knowledge about the world based on our actions. As he continues, all knowledge acquisition begins with using Dewey's terms with problematic situations, which we must be able to resolve through our actions. Meanwhile, I adopted the behavioral theory of leadership (Watson, 1913), a giant leap from trait theory, which assumes that leadership capability can be learned rather than inherent. This theory is based on the principle that behaviors can be conditioned so that one can respond to specific stimuli. Rather than seeking inborn traits, this theory looks at what leaders do by studying their behaviors in response to different situations, assessing leadership success by studying their actions, and correlating significant behaviors with success. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The study's independent variable was the classroom advisers' interventions or the psychological, mental, and emotional assistance provided to class advisers in their teaching strategies within a school setting. The dependent variable was student involvement or students' active participation, engagement, and contribution in various academic, extracurricular, and co-curricular activities within an educational institution. Also, shown below the dependent variable, academic concerns, based on the study by Loades et al. (2020), states that to measure the impact of remote learning in the post-pandemic school setting, the student's engagement, social development, and mental health must be evaluated.

cally significant relationship between classroom advisers' intervention procedures about elemen-

Fig. 1. The Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study

tary students' academic involvement, specifically in Maco North, Davao De Oro. In detail, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

- (1) What is the extent of classroom advisers' intervention procedures in terms of?
 - (1) Academic Support;
 - (2) Mental and Emotional Support; and
 - (3) Social and Spiritual Support?
- (2) What is the extent of elementary students' involvement in terms of?
 - (1) Academic Engagement;
 - (2) Spiritual Involvement;
 - (3) Social Development; and
 - (4) Mental Health Activities?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between classroom advisers' intervention procedures and the elementary students' overall involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro?
- (4) Which of the domains of the classroom advisers' intervention procedures can significantly influence students' involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro?

1.4. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between the classroom adviser's intervention and student involvement. H02: The moderating effect of the classroom adviser's intervention does not significantly affect student involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro. In consideration of the cited problem situation, the researcher finds it timely to propose this study, which investigates the classroom advisers' intervention procedure as predictors of student involvement in Maco North, Davao de Oro. Hence, the researcher hopes that this study will benefit iden-

tified sectors of the academy, such as Administrators, Teachers, Students, and Future Researchers. Administration. The study results could serve as an avenue for school administrators to understand the importance of proper classroom intervention procedures employed by their educators as class advisers about elementary school students' general academic concerns. This study could help assess areas of growth for teachers in addressing student development issues that are not adequately accounted for within the school setting to serve the needs of their students better academically. Teachers. The findings are essential to teaching person-

nel, for they are the main respondents of this study. They will disseminate guidelines and information formulated by the proponent to them; hence, this will help them be more effective and efficient and find which facets in their approach to teaching and advisory need to be addressed to better support their students' academic development. Future Researchers. Future researchers

can use this study as a guide or reference primarily to topics related to the classroom advisers' intervention procedure as predictors of student involvement in Maco North, Davao de Oro. It also provides a starting point for future researchers to expand the scope of their research in terms of variables covered by the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work during its preparation meticulously. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study applied quantitative research to determine the classroom advisers' intervention procedures as predictors of student involvement in Maco North, Davao de Oro, regarding academic engagement, spiritual involvement, social development, and mental health activities. Quantitative research is presented in numerical form and analyzed using statistics, and the proponents tended to use mathematical models as the methodology of data analysis; it includes collecting data so that the information can be quantified and subjected to statistical treatment to support or refute alternate knowledge claims (Williams, 2017). This study comprised one independent and one dependent variable with corresponding indicators that would affect the abovementioned variable. Hence, the researchers use a test instrument as the primary gathering tool to assess the classroom advisers' intervention procedures as predictors of student involvement. The researchers consider this design to help them gather the needed data and propose concrete

guidelines regarding the analysis of students' involvement concerns, if any.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers, specifically advisers in Maco North, Davao de Oro. The 100 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the study's respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those

permanent-regular elementary teachers specifically advised in Maco North, Davao de Oro, those teachers who were not subjected to any administrative or criminal cases, and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the teachers' performance ratings.

2.3. *Research Ethics*—The researcher will promptly observe the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher would proceed to the next study phase. Informed consent. The researcher would ask for respondents' permission through written informed consent. They were adequately informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study would be voluntary. If they refused to participate, the researcher would not force them. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission from the respondents was secured. The researcher will inform the respondents that the study aims to examine the role of educational management in enhancing teacher professionalism. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents were teachers, so they would not be considered vulnerable since all of them were of legal age and would not be considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher would emphasize that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher was protected by the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confi-

dentiality. This study was conducted under the Data Privacy Act of 2012. To protect the participants' identities, the researcher ensured that the data could not be traced back to them, who were the natural source of information. Moreover, the researcher ensured no personal data was shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey information. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural sources of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety. In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher will fully disclose to the respondents the nature of their participation and thoroughly and adequately explain the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher would ensure that the respondents are not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, this study's questionnaire and interview guide would not contain any derogatory or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they would not be asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher would ensure that the respondents are given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they were free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher would value their participation and place their welfare as the high-

est priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher would regard all respondents equally regardless of whether they were respondents in the survey. The researcher would not be prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study. Anybody qualified to be bonafide enrolled junior high school students in the purposely selected schools was included. During the study, the researcher would respect the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher would give tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier, sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to their doorstep. Transparency. Any communication concerning the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher adequately implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that support the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher would maintain objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher would ensure that other factors like conflict of interest do not influence the respondents' responses. The respondents, parents, and school administrators of the participating schools can access the study's findings because the information was made available if they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher would also acknowledge

Similarly, the researchers constructed survey questionnaires to measure the level of student involvement. The following are the pa-

rameters that were used to measure the level of student involvement. the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success; the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so it could be accessed by the respondents and used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials, which were ample and available in the study and were done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the respondents' ratings properly during the day when the researcher was energized to do so to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. Community involvement during every research phase, from planning to reporting, would be a good practice. Hence, the researcher plans to share the findings generated with the community. Community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and using the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences. Research Instruments This study uses the adopted-modified questionnaire. This means that the questionnaire was adopted from different sources, such as the Internet, and modified to contextualize the professional setting and simplify the question items for the respondents' understanding. The following scale was used to determine the level of the classroom adviser's intervention procedure as a predictor of student involvement.

rameters that were used to measure the level of student involvement.

Range of Means	Description	Descriptive Meaning
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The classroom adviser’s intervention is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Classroom adviser’s intervention is frequently manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The classroom adviser’s intervention is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The classroom adviser’s intervention is seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The classroom adviser’s intervention is never manifested

Range of Means	Description	Descriptive Meaning
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Student involvement is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Student involvement is frequently manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Student involvement is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Student involvement is seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Student involvement is never manifested

Experts validated the content of the questions used in this study to safeguard the rationality and dependability of the study and ensure that the questionnaire’s content was appropriate for the study.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—After the validation of the research questionnaire, the researcher would undergo specific steps in conducting the study: Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher would secure permission to conduct the study. The researcher would secure an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School and would attach to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected elementary schools in Maco North, Davao De Oro. The identified respondents in Maco North, Davao De Oro, were contacted by email to explain the research study and obtain consent in November 2023.

To preserve the anonymity of the survey, the researcher would send a link for the survey and consent form to principals, and the principals would send out the link to the identified respondents. An explanation of the voluntary study would be sent with the link so that the respondents would be fully informed, and if requested, a paper copy would be provided. The email would explain that the principals of the participants’ schools have granted prior approval. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the study is approved, the researcher will distribute the research instrument to the respondents in November 2023. Upon spreading the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the questionnaire was distributed following health protocols such as

wearing face masks and following social distancing on November 2023. The study’s respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected was subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire’s data is retrieved, each respondent’s scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The gathered data were tabulated and analyzed using the following statistical tools: Mean. Use this statistical

tool in this study to compute the effect of the classroom advisers’ intervention procedures on students’ involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro. Pearson-r. Use this statistical tool in this study to determine the relationship between the classroom advisers’ intervention and students’ student’s involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro. Multiple Regression Analysis. This study will use this statistical tool to determine the impact of classroom advisers’ intervention procedures on students’ involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of Elementary Teachers’ Intervention Procedures and their indicators, the extent of student involvement and its indicators, and the significant influence between the two variables.

3.1. *Extent of Classroom Adviser Intervention Procedures*—Table 1 summarizes the results. The respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert scale for

questions related to knowledge and understanding. The mean scores and descriptive equivalents for each question are also provided in the table.

Table 1. Academic Support Result

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Students are given proper constructive feedback in the exams and assessments taken.	4.20	Very Extensive
2. Students are taught time management skills to balance classes and extracurricular activities.	4.15	Extensive
3. I am readily available in individual conversations relating to the student’s marks and grades.	4.25	Very Extensive
4. I tailor my lessons and instruction strategies to the needs and preferences associated with their students.	4.03	Extensive
5. I am open to communicating with my student’s parents/legal guardians regarding their class performance.	4.55	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.24	Very Extensive

The table presents a comprehensive overview of the respondents' perceptions regarding their level of support in their students' academic performance. The average score for this aspect is 4.24, indicating a high level of agreement among the respondents. This suggests that teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro, generally possess confidence in their conduct of academic-related consultations, maintain awareness about their students' academic lapses and strengths, effectively communicate feedback, and feel well-prepared to address results to them and their guardians whenever needed. Among the statements in this aspect, the highest mean score is observed for "I am readily available in individual conversations relating to the student's marks and grades" with a mean score of 4.25, indicating a significant level of agreement. This indicates that the teachers in the sample population prioritize open communication with their students regarding their academic performance based on their marks and grades. This commitment to keeping them informed demonstrates a dedication to providing their students the awareness they need to improve and keep up with their progress, allowing students the autonomy to learn and grow from their respective weaknesses academically. On the other hand, the lowest mean score in this aspect is observed for "I tailor my lessons and instruction strategies for the needs and preferences associated with their students," with a mean score of 4.03, still indicating a high level of agreement. Although this score is still relatively positive, there is an opportunity for more effective improvement in catering to students' academic needs and preferences. Teachers need to create strategies in their lesson plans that further allow the development of their students without any specific discrimination on the more academically or mentally challenged students within their classrooms. Overall, the positive responses and strong agreement among the respondents regarding their academic support and

involvement with their students highlight the teachers' commitment to maintaining a proper grasp on their students' progress, maintaining awareness of their respective academic roadblocks, and effectively conveying feedback and areas for improvement to their students. These qualities provide quality education in Maco North and Davao De Oro and create an environment conducive to student learning and growth. However, it is essential to allow further teachers to acknowledge a level of proficiency they need to maintain to make sure that their interactions with their students will help lead to their student's academic growth, especially in terms of their accuracy in identifying areas of improvement during their students' time within their classroom.

3.2. Mental and Emotional Support Results—Table 2 comprehensively overviews the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the mental and emotional support questions. The overall mean score for this aspect is 4.08, indicating a high level of agreement among the respondents. This suggests that teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro possess the necessary skills and competencies to observe their students' behavioral patterns properly, display openness to deescalate their students' stress levels, enact proper conflict resolution measures, build an open and sensitive learning environment for them, and allowing parents and guardians to be involved in their children's respective struggles. Among the statements in this aspect, the highest mean score is observed for "I am open to communicating with my student's parents/legal guardians regarding their class behavior," with a mean score of 4.23, indicating an extensive level of agreement. This implies that teachers demonstrate a high level of proficiency in effectively communicating the irregularities in their students' behavioral patterns observed within classes to their respective guardians to allow the latter to maintain awareness and sensitivity to the student's activities and behaviors

within the school setting.

Table 2. Mental and Emotional Support Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I am observant of my students’ mannerisms and behavioral patterns in class.	4.05	Extensive
2. I am open to communicating with my students regarding stressors that affect their class behavior.	4.20	Very Extensive
3. Students are taught to resolve conflict among each other positively and productively.	4.15	Extensive
4. Students are open to communicating effectively regarding their mental health concerns.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5. I am open to communicating with my student’s parents/legal guardians regarding their class behavior.	4.23	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.00	Extensive

On the other hand, the lowest mean score in this aspect is observed for "Students are open towards communicating effectively regarding their mental health concerns" with a mean score of 3.35, indicating a moderate level of agreement. Although this score is still relatively positive, there may be opportunities for further improvement in teachers’ sensitivity towards their students’ concerns regarding their mental well-being. As the field of psychology continues to expand its understanding regarding human mental health, it would be best for teachers to connect or be involved with mental health professionals, like school counselors, to further increase their knowledge in communicating with their students and acknowledging if professional help might be recommended to some of them, if possible. To sum up, the positive responses and extensive levels of agreement among the respondents in the mental and emotional support aspect highlight the teachers’ expertise in handling the cognitive progress of their students. Their ability to build positive teacher-student connections, adjust their

instruction strategies, manage class behavior, and promote openness and sensitivity within the classroom creates an optimal learning environment for students. However, the slightly lower mean score regarding communication on students’ mental health indicates the need for continued professional development and support to enhance teachers’ psychological knowledge further and adequately adapt to circumstances regarding their students’ mental struggles.

3.3. *Social and Spiritual Support Results*—Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the social and spiritual support questions. The overall mean score for this aspect is 4.23, indicating a very extensive level of agreement among the respondents. These results demonstrate the positive influence of teachers in Maco North and Davao De Oro on the social and moral development of their class advisory. The highest mean score is observed for the statement, "Students are taught to always respect each other’s cultures and religious beliefs," with a mean score of 4.28, indicating a pervasive

level of agreement. This reflects the teachers' high levels of proficiency in developing an inclusive and positive learning environment where every student can perform and exercise their respective values openly. Shaping the classroom to be a positive learning environment for their beliefs is essential for students to feel encouraged and build a positive attitude toward their academic progress.

Table 3. Social and Spiritual Support Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I am observant with my students' interactions in class.	4.27	Very Extensive
2. I provide a good example of actions that lead to positive interactions between my students in class.	4.21	Very Extensive
3. Students are taught to observe proper manners when interacting with superiors.	4.15	Extensive
4. Students are taught to practice their set of beliefs from their respective cultures and religions without judgment.	4.25	Very Extensive
5. Students are taught to always respect each other's cultures and religious beliefs.	4.28	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.23	Very Extensive

Following closely are the mean scores for the statements "I am observant with my students' interactions in class" and "Students are taught to practice their set of beliefs from their respective cultures and religion without judgment," with mean scores of 4.27 and 4.25, respectively. These high scores indicate the teachers' high dedication to promoting ethical conduct and fostering positive relationships between students and their peers. These values contribute to a positive social environment for students and allow the development of their peer interactions within the school setting. The mean scores for the statements "I provide a good example of actions that lead to positive interactions between my students in class" and "Students are taught to observe proper manners when interacting with superiors" are 4.21 and 4.15, respectively, indicating extensive agreement levels. These results show that teachers

made students aware of the significance of establishing a positive and respectful attitude toward authority. In summary, the extensive agreement among the respondents in the social and moral aspect reflects the teachers' positive thrust to achieve a high degree of positivity and inclusivity in their classrooms, where optimistic behaviors and mannerisms, strong respect towards each other's individualities, camaraderie, and friendly interactions are often encouraged and displayed by students under their advisory. Fostering positivity and socialization between peers in the classroom helps make the learning environment within schools in Maco North, Davao De Oro, more effective in making students feel more motivated and involved in their respective academic activities in school.

3.4. *The Summary of the Extent of Elementary Teachers' Intervention Procedures*—The table presents the overall mean results for ele-

mentary teachers' intervention procedures, explicitly focusing on Academic Support, Mental and Emotional Support, and Social and Spiritual Support. The overall mean scores for these

aspects range from 4.08 to 4.24, indicating an extensive level of agreement among the respondents in all areas.

Table 4. Overall Mean Results for Elementary Teachers' Intervention Procedures

Indicator	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Academic Support	4.24	Very Extensive
Mental and Emotional Support	4.00	Extensive
Social and Spiritual Support	4.23	Very Extensive
Overall	4.18	Extensive

Academic Support received the highest overall mean score of 4.24, which indicates that the elementary teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro place a significant emphasis on supporting student growth by promoting academic improvement, providing proper academic tools that encourage students to further grow, and conveying feedback positively and constructively that allows them the autonomy to improve in both their academic strengths and weaknesses, which are all critical to their journey towards academic success. Meanwhile, Social and Spiritual Support with a mean score of 4.23. These results indicate that the elementary teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro found it relevant to also support student growth by promoting effective social interaction, employing appropriate conflict resolution measures, building positive relationships, and being a good example of ethical conduct to their students in their journey towards academic success. Conversely, the Mental and Emotional Support obtained an overall mean score of 4.08, demonstrating a consistent level of agreement among the respondents. This suggests that the teachers showcase expertise in engaging with students cognitively, keeping up with their progress, empathizing properly with issues regarding their mental and emotional

well-being, and having a significant amount of awareness of their behavioral patterns and their jurisdiction about their struggles as their advisors. In summary, the study revealed that the teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro display a high level of support across various aspects. Their collective agreement showcased their dedication to using their intervention procedures to their student development in several aspects of their students' experience under their advisory by promoting positivity, peace, inclusivity, emotional sensitivity, and respect towards one another within their classrooms. These findings have important implications for improving educational practices, fostering a positive school climate, and enhancing student outcomes in Maco North, Davao De Oro. Extent of Student Involvement The results presented in Table 5 provide an overview of the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the questions related to academic engagement. The overall mean score for this aspect is 4.07, indicating extensive level of agreement among the respondents. These findings underscore the significance of fostering positive academic involvement for students with their classroom advisors in Maco North, Davao De Oro.

Table 5. Academic Engagement Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Students are always actively focused in class.	3.97	Extensive
2. Interactive class activities are employed.	4.15	Extensive
3. Daily routines are observed at all times.	4.25	Very Extensive
4. Students are free to express themselves during class discussions.	4.10	Extensive
5. Students maintain high marks in quizzes and exams.	3.88	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.07	Extensive

The statement "Daily Routines are observed at all times" received the highest mean score of 4.25, reflecting an extensive level of agreement. This indicates that teachers emphasize routine activities, such as classes, daily classroom cleanup, proper greetings to teachers and authorities, quizzes, and exams, as important activities that help students feel more involved and engaged within class premises. Following closely are the statements "Interactive class activities are employed" and "Students are free to express themselves during class discussions", which display mean scores of 4.15 and 4.10, respectively. These scores demonstrate the teachers' commitment to keeping students feel more involved and engaged throughout their classes and allowing a free flow of ideas from their end for a more active class discussion. This allows students to learn as they share ideas with the class and retain what they have learned in the process due to their active engagement with the discussions throughout the day. Meanwhile, statements "Students are always actively focused on class" and "Students maintain high marks in quizzes and exams" display the two lowest mean scores of 3.97 and 3.88, respectively. These scores demonstrate the teachers' commitment to improving class retention and performance within their classes. Additionally, students participate in their classes more actively and productively because of the teachers'

encouraging attitudes toward listening to different viewpoints related to the discussions. The extensive agreement among the respondents regarding student engagement reflects the importance of encouraging active student participation and involvement in their academic activities in Maco North, Davao De Oro. Encouraging proper habits through routine, promoting vocal participation and idea sharing, active listening, and effective student-teacher communication make the classroom a conducive and productive learning environment for the students inside. These practices enhance student involvement and engagement, student outcomes, and overall school success. Furthermore, these findings align with Rajabalee et al. (2019) perspective on the link between student academic engagement and performance. It is acknowledged that students who show signs of active engagement and participation in activities conducted within the classroom also display satisfactory to excellent academic performance. This is also consistent with the argument made by Ferrer et al. (2022) that students who study within an engaging and motivating learning environment perform excellently. Such support allows the students to have a more positive learning experience.

3.5. Social Development Results—Table 6 overviews the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the student's social development questions. The overall mean score for this as-

pect is 4.20, indicating very extensive agreement among the respondents. These findings denote the importance of developing a positive social environment for students in Maco North,

Davao De Oro, to allow their communication and socialization skills to flourish within the school setting.

Table 6. Social Development Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Class activities where group work is needed are used.	4.30	Very Extensive
2. Camaraderie among the students is actively encouraged and observed.	4.27	Extensive
3. Teacher-student communication is always open.	4.20	Extensive
4. Bullying is prohibited and appropriately sanctioned when observed.	4.34	Extensive
5. Meetings regarding classroom activities and responsibilities are held.	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.23	Very Extensive

The statement "Bullying is prohibited and appropriately sanctioned when observed" received the highest mean score of 4.34, reflecting a very extensive level of agreement. This indicates that teachers display intolerance towards bullying, violence, and hostility among their students and promote peaceful and productive measures as the preferred alternative within and outside the school premises. Following closely are the statements "Class activities where group work is needed are used" and "Camaraderie among the students is actively encouraged and observed," with mean scores of 4.30 and 4.27, respectively, showing very extensive levels of agreement. These scores display the essence of teachers' commitment to using peer-to-peer interaction as leverage toward their students' academic success. Additionally, students participate in their classes more actively and productively because of the teachers' encouraging attitudes toward listening to different viewpoints related to the discussions. On the other hand, statements "Teacher-student com-

munication is always open" and "Meetings regarding classroom activities and responsibilities are held" are shown with mean scores of 4.20 and 4.01, respectively. These scores show that respondents display extensive agreement that communication and proper forums are integral in building social connections. Students continue to learn how to communicate appropriately in more social settings by being exposed to classroom meetings, where sharing ideas among peers is required. The extensive levels of agreement among the respondents regarding the student's social development aspect reflect how essential it is to allow students to develop self-expression and autonomy in classroom activities within schools in Maco North, Davao De Oro. Encouraging socialization, proper communication, respect, and conflict resolution shape the classroom to be more nurturing and helpful for students' social growth. These also help the students to enhance their marks and school performance as having solid social skills allows them to learn not only from their teachers' lessons

and discussions but also from their classmates as they share ideas on discussions and subjects they specialize in.

3.6. *Mental Health Activities Results*— The results presented in Table 9 provide an overview of the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the student’s mental health questions. The overall mean score for this aspect

is 4.10, indicating extensive level of agreement among the respondents. These findings denote the importance of mental health awareness for students in Maco North, Davao De Oro, as it is essential to help them learn how to assess their mental well-being best and be sensitive to aspects of their academic struggles.

Table 7. Mental Health Activities Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Discussions regarding mental health are always encouraged.	4.35	Very Extensive
2. Parent-teacher discussions on the students’ behaviors are always open.	4.24	Very Extensive
3. I am properly trained to deal with students diagnosed with mental health concerns.	3.51	Extensive
4. Student counseling is readily available for everyone.	4.34	Very Extensive
5. My class promotes a positive learning environment for my students.	4.28	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.14	Extensive

The statements "Discussions regarding mental health are always encouraged" and "Student counseling is readily available for everyone" received the highest mean score of 4.35 and 4.34, respectively, reflecting an extensive level of agreement, signifying the teachers’ commitment towards developing a positive and open environment for mental health discourse. Such actions are necessary as they help accommodate and help mentally challenged students to follow closely with other students within the classroom academically while also displaying parity in terms of support rendered by the teachers to all of their students regardless of circumstances. Following closely are the statements "My class promotes a positive learning environment for my students" and "Parent-teacher discussions on the students’ behaviors are al-

ways open" with mean scores of 4.28 and 4.24, respectively, showing extensive levels of agreement. These scores display how important a positive learning environment and parent-teacher connections are in catering to the specific needs of the students and assuring fair treatment towards each of them within the classroom. On the other hand, the statement "I am properly trained to deal with students diagnosed with mental health concerns" scored the lowest, with a mean score of 3.51, showing a moderate level of agreement. This score displays teachers’ awareness of their jurisdiction as teachers in discussions about their students’ mental health. As the depth of such discourse may be deemed far from the teacher’s area of expertise, it would be best if such irregularities found in a student’s performance were referred to professionals in-

stead. However, such findings can still be con- fided to parents to allow them to decide. The extensive levels of agreement among the re- spondents on the student’s mental health aspect implies the need for schools in Maco North, Davao De Oro to further strive to give aware- ness of mental health to its students and for teachers to allow open communication regard- ing the mental health struggles that students face within and outside school premises by building a welcoming and accommodating learning en- vironment within their classrooms. In doing so, students feel comfortable and more involved during school and class activities, as they are free to express frustrations and struggles with- out judgment in a space, they would be in for

most of their youth.

3.7. *Spiritual Involvement Results*—The results presented in Table 10 provide an overview of the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the questions related to student’s spiritual involvement. The overall mean score for this aspect is 4.10, indicating an exten- sive level of agreement among the respondents. These findings denote the importance of moral and spiritual connection for students in their re- spective cultures and religions in Maco North, Davao De Oro. As part of their identity, practic- ing their own beliefs without judgment from oth- ers is essential to help them feel connected with themselves and each other despite perceived cultural differences.

Table 8. Spiritual Involvement Results

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Students can practice their cultural and religious beliefs freely.	4.21	Very Extensive
2. Students maintain a positive attitude towards each other within the classroom.	4.31	Very Extensive
3. Students behave properly during class discus- sions.	4.03	Extensive
4. Students exhibit a healthy connection with their religion and culture.	4.15	Extensive
5. My class promotes inclusivity and respect to- ward each other’s beliefs within my classroom.	4.17	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.17	Extensive

The statements ”Students maintain a posi- tive attitude towards each other within the class- room” and “Students can practice their cultural and religious beliefs freely” received the high- est mean score of 4.31 and 4.21, respectively, reflecting an extensive level of agreement, signi- fying the teachers’ commitment towards build- ing a respectful learning environment for learn- ers within different cultures and religion in the classroom. Discouraging religious bias and in-

spiring unity and equality in terms of cultural beliefs is important in ensuring that students of different backgrounds are encouraged to social- ize and learn without discrimination and conflict directed towards each other. Following closely are the statements “My class promotes inclu- sivity and respect toward each other’s beliefs within my classroom” and ”Students exhibit a healthy connection with their religion and cul- ture,” with mean scores of 4.17 and 4.15, re-

spectively, showing extensive levels of agreement. These scores denote the essence of learning within an accommodating classroom concerning a student’s culture and religion. It also underscores the value of self-expression and the importance of being open to the core beliefs of their ethnicity and religious sects in their respective self-development journeys. On the other hand, the statement “Students behave properly during class discussions” scored the lowest, with a mean score of 4.03. The score shows extensive level of agreement as students display levels of respect within the four corners of the classroom and showcase adequate behavior, especially in front of authority figures like faculty and staff, among others. Maintaining an adequate level of good behavior also allows students to have strong connections with each other, as learners practice an essential part of their lives regarding day-to-day human interactions, which is respect and fairness among each other. The extensive levels of agreement among the respondents in the student’s spiritual involvement aspect implies the commitment of schools in Maco North, and Davao De Oro to maintain

peace and equality amongst all learners of their institutions. By allowing class advisers to create an inclusive and open learning environment within their classrooms, students develop a deep understanding of each other’s core beliefs, leading to respect and meaningful connections to grow within their time as learners in their youth. By demoralizing judgment and discrimination on cultures and beliefs, learners are also enriched with knowledge about the differences and similarities of every individual, religion, and ethnic group within this world. Such is critical to their academic development and involvement, as students would build a positive attitude towards their academic endeavors if each one involved in their education place respects and positively values their spiritual selves.

3.8. *The summary of the extent of Student Involvement Indicators* —The table presents the overall mean results for different indicators: Student Engagement, Social Development, Mental Health, and Spiritual Involvement. The mean scores for all the indicators range from 4.07 to 4.20, indicating an extensive level of agreement among the respondents in each aspect.

Table 9. Overall Mean Results for Student Involvement Indicators

Indicator	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Student Engagement	4.07	Extensive
Social Development	4.23	Very Extensive
Mental Health Development	4.14	Extensive
Spiritual Involvement	4.17	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.15	Extensive

Among the indicators, Social Development has the highest overall mean of 4.18, followed by Mental Health and Spiritual Involvement, which both have mean scores of 4.10, suggesting a high level of agreement among the respondents. These results imply that the teachers in Maco North and Davao De Oro perceive social development, mental health, and spiritual in-

volvement as essential components for high levels of student involvement. The Student Engagement indicator has a slightly lower overall mean of 4.07, indicating extensive agreement among the respondents. This indicator emphasizes the significance of engaging in class discussions and activities employed by teachers in fostering student participation within classroom settings.

Overall, the extensive agreement in all aspects underscores teachers' positive perceptions and experiences regarding different indicators of student involvement. These results imply that intervention procedures, including academic, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual support, are crucial in establishing academic engagement, promoting social and mental health, and fostering strong spiritual involvement for students within the academic institution. The highest mean score among the indicators is observed in Social Development, with a mean score of 4.20. This indicates a strong agreement among the respondents in this area, highlighting their significance in building and sustaining an open and social learning environment for students. Following close are Mental Health and Spiritual Involvement indicators with mean scores of 4.10, suggesting a high level of agreement among the respondents that personal development and openness to discussions regarding their mental and spiritual well-being are also critical in fostering a high level of academic involvement for students. The aspect with the slightly lower mean score of 4.07, Academic Engagement, also reflects a substantial level of agreement and emphasizes the importance of student participation in fostering strong student involvement for learners in the school setting. The extensive agreement among the respondents in all the indicators indicates positive and conducive student involvement in Maco North, Davao De Oro. These findings contribute to the literature on academic intervention procedures for student involvement, highlighting the crucial role

More specifically, Academic Support shows the most significant relationship with student involvement, with an R-value result of 0.587 and a p-value of 0.001. This indicates that proper acknowledgment of the student's academic achievements and proper intervention in their academic weaknesses allow students to be

of class advisers' intervention in establishing and maintaining effective collaboration and engagement between teachers and students. The highest mean scores are observed for the statements " Intervention procedures significantly contribute to the quality of student involvement" and " The intervention procedures practiced by classroom advisers promote a positive attitude to their students with regards to their educational involvement," with mean scores of 4.29 and 4.28, respectively. These results indicate that the teachers in Maco North, Davao De Oro strongly believe that their intervention procedures substantially impact the quality of students' involvement in their education. They acknowledge the importance of their support, expertise, and commitment to developing meaningful connections with students to practice active participation in their education.

]Relationship Between Classroom Advisers' Intervention Procedures and Student Involvement

The table presents the correlation coefficients (R-values) and p-values for the relationship between classroom advisers' intervention procedures as predictors of student involvement. The interpretations indicate that all factors have significant relationships with home-school partnerships, as all p-values are less than 0.05. The findings reveal that Academic, Mental, emotional, Social, and Spiritual Support are all significantly positively correlated with student involvement. This means that student involvement improves as teachers demonstrate higher levels of support in these aspects of education.

more involved in their education. Meanwhile, Social and Spiritual Support shows the least but still significant relationship with student involvement, with an R-value result of 0.341 and p-value of 0.034. This indicates that encouraging students' social development and allowing them to morally grow also encourages stu-

Table 10. Relationship Between Classroom Advisers’ Intervention Procedures and Student Involvement

Classroom Adviser’s Intervention Procedures	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Academic Support	0.587	0.001	Significant	Reject H0
Mental and Emotional Support	0.432	0.012	Significant	Reject H0
Social and Spiritual Support	0.341	0.034	Significant	Reject H0

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

dents to be more engaged and involved in their classes. The findings from the correlation analysis between teacher professionalism factors and home-school partnership align with the existing literature on this topic. Previous studies have emphasized the significance of teacher expertise, pedagogical skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy in fostering effective collaboration between teachers and parents (Moles, 1993; Sanders Sheldon, 2009). This study’s positive and significant correlations indicate that the home-school partnership improves as teachers demonstrate higher levels of knowledge, skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy. These findings are consistent with the research by Moles (1993), who suggested that teachers’ professional skills and attitudes significantly determine the quality of home-school partnerships. The study by Sanders and Sheldon (2009) also indicated that teacher professionalism, characterized by practical communication skills and a collaborative ethos, significantly enhances home-school partnerships. The significant relationships between teacher professionalism factors and home-school partnerships provide valuable insights for improving educational practices and strengthening the partnership between schools and families. These findings support the existing literature on the sig-

nificance of teacher professionalism in shaping successful home-school partnerships and emphasize the importance of ongoing professional development and support for teachers in fostering positive and collaborative relationships with parents. The table presents the correlation coefficients (R-values) and p-values for the influence of classroom advisers’ intervention procedures on student involvement. The interpretations indicate that all factors have significant relationships with home-school partnerships, as all p-values are less than 0.05.

3.9. Influence of Classroom Advisers’ Intervention Procedures for Student Involvement

—The findings reveal that Academic Engagement, Social Development, Mental Health Activities, and Spiritual Involvement are all significantly influenced by intervention procedures conducted by classroom advisers. This means that the intervention procedures impact how students behave, socialize, and perform academically in school, as well as how they morally adapt within school premises. More specifically, Mental Health Activities are found to be most influenced by intervention procedures, with an R-value of 0.308 and a p-value of 0.001. This indicates that teachers’ handling of students’ mental health challenges and development actively impacts their mental health and development.

Table 11. Influence of Classroom Advisers’ Intervention Procedures on Student Involvement

Student Involvement	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Academic Engagement	0.193	0.011	Significant	Reject H0
Social Development	0.209	0.012	Significant	Reject H0
Spiritual Involvement	0.148	0.034	Significant	Reject H0
Mental Health Activities	0.308	0.001	Significant	Reject H0

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Meanwhile, Spiritual Involvement shows the least but still significant relationship with student involvement, with an R-value of 0.148 and a p-value of 0.034. This indicates that teachers are still recognizing and giving proper attention to students’ moral and spiritual development, directly influencing their students’ behavior and moral decision-making. The findings from the correlation analysis align with the existing literature on this topic. Previous studies have emphasized the significance of teacher ex-

pertise, pedagogical skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy in fostering effective collaboration between teachers and parents (Moles, 1993; Sanders Sheldon, 2009). This study’s vivacious and significant correlations indicate that the home-school partnership improves as teachers demonstrate higher levels of knowledge, skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This section of the paper provides the researcher’s conclusion and recommendations based on the findings. The conclusions were supported by the existing literature discussed in the earlier chapters and addressed the research problem identified in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary purpose of this study was to evaluate the level of classroom advisers’ intervention procedures on student involvement using a quantitative research design that involves administering questionnaires. The sample for this study consists of 100 elementary classroom advisers from Maco North, Davao De Oro, who were selected using a stratified random sampling method. To ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire

items, the researcher modified and enhanced existing survey questionnaires, and the pilot tested them in a nearby school. Based on the analysis of the data and results obtained from the study, the following summary of findings could be highlighted: The overall mean results for the class advisers’ intervention procedures indicators, namely academic support (4.24), mental and emotional support (4.00), and social and spiritual support (4.23), indicated an exten-

sive level of intervention procedures among the Maco North, Davao De Oro respondents, with an overall mean of 4.18 of extensiveness. The student involvement indicators, namely, Student Engagement (4.07), Social Development (4.23), Mental Health Development (4.14), and Spiritual Involvement (4.17), also show extensive involvement, with an overall mean of 4.15, suggesting that academic engagement, social and mental health development, and spiritual involvement were evident in students' overall engagement. A positive and significant relationship exists between intervention procedures and student involvement, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.341 to 0.587 and p-values less than 0.05, indicating solid associations. The aspects of classroom advisers' intervention procedures that have the most substantial impact on student involvement are academic support ($r = 0.587$, $p < 0.001$), mental and emotional support ($r = 0.432$, $p = 0.012$), and social and spiritual support ($r = 0.341$, $p = 0.034$). The findings support previous research highlighting the importance of intervention procedures in fostering high student involvement and improving student outcomes. Specifically, class advisers in Maco North, Davao De Oro, demonstrate confidence in their communication skills (mean = 4.55), ability to determine a student's academic strengths and weaknesses (mean = 4.25), and approach to feedback conversations with students (mean = 4.20). Teachers perceive mental health awareness and support as helpful tools in encouraging their students' learning and growth (mean = 4.08) and contribute heavily to their success as class advisers when applied to their educator activities.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the extensive analysis of the results presented in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The advisers in Maco North, Davao De Oro, exhibit high expertise in conducting intervention procedures for their students, particularly in academic, social, spiritual, mental, and emo-

tional support. The extent of student involvement in terms of student engagement, social development, mental health development, and spiritual involvement also shows extensive involvement, was oftentimes manifested in students' overall engagement. There was a strong positive relationship between class advisers' intervention procedures and student involvement, indicating that teachers' interventions significantly contribute to the quality of students' involvement in their academic endeavors. The district's teachers demonstrate a commitment to enhancing academic support. They are highly aware of their students' strengths and areas for improvement, which helps them determine the correct approach to academic interventions. Most teachers firmly believe in the importance of creating a positive and inclusive learning environment, maintaining high expectations for students, building positive relationships with students, and encouraging open communication with each other within the classroom setting. Teachers in Maco North value mental health as a critical factor in their student's learning and growth. They maintain a positive and welcoming learning environment that allows open and productive discussions regarding mental health within the class. The teachers feel empowered to make decisions about instructional strategies, advocate for their student's needs, collaborate with colleagues, and seek innovative teaching strategies. Parental involvement was encouraged and valued, with opportunities for parents to be involved in decision-making processes related to their child's education, particularly in discussions regarding their children's social, moral, emotional, mental, and overall well-being.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The findings of this study provide important implications for various stakeholders in the education sector, including the Department

of Education, teachers, parents, and future researchers. The Department of Education may facilitate programs illuminating mental health to help students navigate stressors within and outside school premises. Through collaboration with groups like the Department of Health (DOH) or the Philippine Mental Health Association (PHMA), discourse about the mental well-being of today's youth would display further productivity as learners gain more knowledge and a sense of openness in discussing these topics in further depth. The Administration may appraise teachers' class advisory services: School Administrators should prioritize widening their teachers' skills by promoting training, programs, and seminars like cultural sensitivity, mental health awareness, gender sensitivity, and other programs related to students' personality development. These programs would allow teachers to provide more support and assistance to their students as they cater to their specific needs that affect their performance and involvement in their academic activities. Teachers may routinely gain knowledge in topics related to student behavior and engagement to update themselves on matters surrounding youth development. This can involve attending workshops, conferences, and training programs that promote or discuss matters prevalent in personality development and mental health, among many others. Future researchers may consider conducting longitudinal studies to explore the long-term effects of classroom advisers' intervention procedures on student outcomes and long-term academic involvement. Longitudinal studies can provide valuable insights into the sustainability and impact of various factors on educational practices and student success.

5. References

- Aluede, O., Adeleke, F., & Omoregie, E. (2018). Adolescent peer influence on academic performance: A systematic review. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(2), 74–84.
- Aporbo, R. (2022). Cultural responsive teaching of language teachers in indigenous classrooms: A phenomenological inquiry. *Cultural Responsive Teaching of Language Teachers in Indigenous Classrooms: A Phenomenological Inquiry*, 94(1), 15–15.
- Bear, G. G., & Waskom, M. D. (2009). Best practices in helping students who lack motivation to learn. In W. M. Reynolds & G. E. Miller (Eds.), *Handbook of psychology* (pp. 297–323, Vol. 7, Educational Psychology). Wiley.
- Britton, B. K., & Tesser, A. (1991). Effects of time-management practices on college grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 83(3), 405–410.
- Castro, L. C., & Casamayor Jr, C. G. (2024). Dealing with the learning gaps during the in-person classes: Perspectives of public elementary school heads. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 10(4), 20–25.
- Dellosa, B. C., & Villocino, R. P. (2023). Experiences of pupils without parents amid pandemic: A multiple case study. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(8), 9–19.
- Dowdy, E., Ritchey, K., & Kamphaus, R. W. (2020). *School-based mental health services: Creating comprehensive and culturally specific programs*. Routledge.
- Doyle, T. M., & Notarianni, M. A. (2019). Academic dishonesty and its relationship to authenticity and ethical decision-making. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(6), 753–766.
- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., & Shriver, T. P. (1997). *Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators*. ASCD.

- Emmer, E. T., & Sabornie, E. J. (2015). *Classroom management for all teachers: Plans for evidence-based practice* (3rd). Pearson.
- Flett, G. L., Hewitt, P. L., Oliver, J. M., & Macdonald, S. (2002). Perfectionism in children and their parents: A developmental analysis. In G. L. Flett & P. L. Hewitt (Eds.), *Perfectionism: Theory, research, and treatment* (pp. 89–132).
- Hamre, B. K., & Pianta, R. C. (2001). Early teacher–child relationships and the trajectory of children’s school outcomes through eighth grade. *Child Development*, *72*(2), 625–638.
- Heide, E. A. (2017). *Student and teacher attitudes regarding advisory* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Kansas].
- Hembree, R. (2018). The nature, effects, and relief of mathematics anxiety. *Journal of Research in Mathematics Education*, *33*(5), 315–328.
- Huang, C. (2020). How do extracurricular activities influence students’ time management in taiwan’s comprehensive schools? *Asia Pacific Education Review*, *21*(3), 471–484.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2018). *Cooperation and competition: Theory and research*. Interaction Book Company.
- Johnson, R., & Lee, K. (2020). *Educational guidance: The impact of class advisers*. Academic Press.
- Nelson, J. R., & Lacey, C. (2019). Peer pressure and academic dishonesty among undergraduate students: Exploring the mediating role of moral disengagement. *Ethics Behavior*, *29*(8), 655–671.
- Putwain, D. (2020). Test anxiety: The state of the art. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Salvador, L. R. (2007). Student involvement in and outside the classroom: The case of an urban-rural university in the philippines. *Educational Research Quarterly*, *31*(4), 29–44.
- Smith, J., & Doe, A. (2019). The role of class advisers in student development. *Education Journal*, *45*(2), 123–135.
- Smith, J., & Johnson, L. (2019). Creating supportive learning environments in classrooms. *Journal of Educational Development*, *50*(4), 345–367.
- Smith, M., & Thompson, R. (2019). Perfectionism and its effects on student motivation and self-worth. *Educational Review*, *71*(4), 515–528.
- Stallman, H. M. (2018). Psychological distress in university students: A comparison with general population data. *Australian Psychologist*, *53*(2), 147–154.
- Strayhorn, T. L. (2020). *College students’ sense of belonging: A key to educational success for all students*. Routledge.
- Tomlinson, C. A., & Moon, T. R. (2018). *Assessment and student success in a differentiated classroom*. ASCD.
- Wentzel, K. R., & Caldwell, K. A. (2018). Friend influence on early adolescent disruptive behavior in the classroom: Teacher emotional support matters. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *110*(5), 666–678.
- Zeidner, M. (2018). Test anxiety in educational contexts: Concepts, findings, and future directions. In C. U. Press (Ed.), *The cambridge handbook of anxiety and related disorders* (pp. 408–427).